

Integrating Structural Biology

Instruct-ULTRA

WP6 – Expanding access provision and users services

Lead Beneficiaries: Partner 13 – UU

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Deliverable D6.2: VLE final version available to public

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Project objective

Promote Collaboration between service providers through a virtual laboratory environment (VLE).

Executive summary

The ARIADNE application was designed, developed, and tested as a virtual laboratory environment, in order to improve collaboration between facilities and enhance user experience. ARIADNE functionality was demonstrated as a proof of concept for protein production and biophysics technologies. While the final rollout of ARIADNE to the public was not possible due to a number of technical factors, this project provided valuable insights into the functioning of ARIA and led to specific developments that are of direct value to the user community. To complement the work on ARIADNE, the initial aims of the project were re-imagined in a number of different ways, including improvements to the ARIA internal messaging system, the use of instant messaging applications for cryoEM facility managers, the BBMRI Negotiator tool, and a full User Experience study of the Instruct-ERIC website.

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1. ARIADNE as a mechanism to improve collaboration and user experience

1.1. Introducing ARIADNE

ARIADNE is a software tool that builds upon the pre-existing ARIA system of Instruct-ERIC. ARIADNE creates a virtual lab environment (VLE), a concept that allows users and staff to collaborate in order to provide a bespoke service, more carefully matching users to the most suitable technology. The name ARIADNE is derived from “ARIA Distributed Network Environment”, where ARIA is the project management software developed by Instruct-ERIC to support proposal submission, management, instrument booking and website hosting, among other services.

The concept for the VLE was to improve the user experience, by circumventing the need to choose a specific site for executing experiments, when a service is requested by users. Currently, users are expected to choose the optimal technology platform for their research project. However, feedback has suggested that some of the Instruct-ERIC user base would benefit from interaction with facility managers in planning their experiments, as part of the proposal submission process.

The aim of ARIADNE was thus to match users with the most suitable service for their experiment. The VLE would allow users to have direct contact with multiple facilities, and facility staff in turn could ask more specific questions to the user. This would provide information beyond that of the application form, allowing a more bespoke service for the user. The VLE would allow users to interact via the web to discuss issues related to technical feasibility and choice of methods for their experiment. ARIADNE was conceived by Netherlands Cancer Institute (NKI) a third party to University of Utrecht (P13). NKI were responsible for writing the code for the ARIADNE prototype with input from the Instruct-ERIC software developers in relation to linking with ARIA.

1.2 ARIADNE development and design

The first stage of ARIADNE Development was the VLE design and development, to set up a prototype for the specific use case of protein production. Five open source components¹

¹ Tomcat/Shibboleth IdP (Identity Provider) with LDAP (Lightweight Directory Access Protocol); Apache/Shibboleth SP (Service Provider); MariaDB server (MySQL); Rocket Chat; Checkpoint server in python flask

were utilised, with a key component being Rocket Chat, allowing users to hold discussions in private groups. ARIADNE tests were run from NKI servers, side by side with a local ARIA test website.

A functional prototype was first established for the protein production workflow. In this workflow the user is asked a series of questions about the research project, whereby facility managers from multiple Instruct centres are invited to provide feedback about the technical feasibility of the project, and comment about the type of protein expression system that might be expected to perform best for the particular type of protein production requested by the user. The Facility Manager chat page within the ARIADNE application is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. A screen shot of the ARIADNE application for protein production.

Following initial feedback from facility managers, dialogue between the user and facility managers is enabled, so that joint discussions can take place to decide which centre would be best positioned to take on the project. At the same time, scientific suggestions for best practices could be discussed, resulting in optimal use of resources to perform the best experiments, and sharing of experience between facilities and the users. Within the same chat, time frames and laboratory availability could be discussed. The final step in the ARIADNE workflow is the production of a report to summarise the decisions made, which can then be imported back into the ARIA database as a technical evaluation, to be taken forward as advice for the technical review.

1.3 ARIADNE testing and extension

The ARIADNE system was tested as a proof of concept with two Instruct Centres at NKI (partner 13), STRUBI (partner 2) and a test user. The workflow was carefully assessed, and each member of facility staff could provide feedback about the usability of the application, which was fed back into the project plan for further improvement.

Following the success of the protein production platform on ARIADNE, the application was extended to include biophysical characterisation services. This section was also tested and found to work well.

1.4 ARIADNE conclusion

ARIADNE was clearly established as a proof of concept, demonstrating that a software tool like ARIADNE could enable wider conversations at multiple facilities when a single proposal was submitted.

The final stages of ARIADNE development involved an evaluation by the Instruct-ERIC ARIA development team of the requirements for integrating the underlying code of the prototype into the ARIA management system. This would be necessary for effective public roll out of ARIADNE. Owing to the evolution of the ARIA code in the meantime, as well as future development plans, it was determined that the code developed should not be integrated in the ARIA system. Combined with considerations about the long-term ARIA code base functionality, the decision was made to pause the rollout of ARIADNE to other user bases including the general public.

The initial ARIADNE concept and workings have been passed to the Instruct-ERIC hub for consideration in any future developments of the ARIA system. The development of the functionality will be useful when the next generation of ARIA tools are discussed.

2. Widening the scope to consider other tools to improve collaboration and user experience

Although it was decided that work on ARIADNE would be discontinued, the project has generated value in conceptualising how users could interact with the service providers in Instruct. Therefore, the decision was made to widen the scope of the Instruct ULTRA deliverable to consider other solutions to the issues originally highlighted, including improving collaboration and user experience. This redirection of resources has led to direct improvements in services for the Instruct User Community that are now rolled out to the general public.

2.1 Promote collaboration between service providers by group messaging within ARIA

Beyond ARIADNE, Instruct has found alternative methods to promote dialogue between centres and thereby improve access provision. The first of these is group messaging within the ARIA system, which allows multiple staff members from different centres to communicate and is used most frequently in the proposal review process.

From the first iteration of ARIA, there was a simple messaging service set up, so that any registered users could contact each other (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Internal messaging system within ARIA.

The messaging system is used when research proposals are accepted, for all communications relating to the booking and planning of a research visit.

Significant upgrades to the ARIA messaging service have been implemented during 2020. Firstly, on each technology page within the Instruct-ERIC online catalogue, users are invited to “contact service/technology”. If a user sends a question, this will initiate a message thread that includes all the scientific experts and facility managers for that technology. This new system allows for greater collaboration between users and facility managers and should help users decide which technology and platform to include in their proposal application.

Secondly, group messaging has been enabled alongside workflow steps, where message threads are initiated within “sessions”. Such functionality will allow facility managers to share questions specific to a particular proposal, in a similar way to ARIADNE. Expertise and advice can easily be exchanged among facility managers, which will lead to more efficient proposal management and improved services for users. A final improvement to the ARIA messaging system is integration with email, whereby notification of messages is sent by email, and users can reply directly from their email client.

2.2 Promote collaboration between service providers by Slack instant messaging

A second mechanism to promote collaboration between service providers was to pilot an instant messaging service for the CryoEM facility managers. Instruct initiated a Slack channel for cryoEM, following requests from facility managers for a dedicated messaging channel. Slack² is an instant messaging platform that allows for the creation of chat rooms that can be organised by topic. The cryoEM channel links Instruct facility staff across Europe

² www.slack.com

and other cryoEM users, allowing them to easily communicate, share best practice and collaborate. As of September 2020, the slack channel had over 220 participants, with several new message strings starting up each month. Promoting collaboration and innovation is key in the continued improvement of access provisions across Instruct. As the cryoEM Slack channel has been successful, this can be rolled out for other service types within Instruct.

Figure 3. CryoEM instant messaging service hosted by Slack.

2.3 BBMRI-ERIC Negotiator tool

Although somewhat outside the realms of Instruct-ULTRA, it is relevant to note that staff at Instruct-ERIC (partner 1) have liaised with the BBMRI-ERIC³ team during the development of an online tool, which has similar functionality to those of a VLE such as ARIADNE.

The BBMRI Negotiator⁴ is a communication and access negotiation platform connecting biobankers with researchers requesting samples and/or data. It is not always possible for biobanks to accurately represent the data that can be obtained, due to restrictions on the information that can be made public as well as due to the costs of a priori data extraction from primary systems for all the patients and donors. This means that key resources for medical research may not be so easily discovered and accessed by researchers. The BBMRI negotiator platform aims to 'enable effective access negotiation when some or all resources are only vaguely characterised'. This will simplify the process of obtaining information on sample and data availability across multiple biobanks.

³ <https://bbmri-eric.eu>

⁴ <https://negotiator.bbmri-eric.eu>

Figure 4. BBMRI Negotiator web page.

The initial phase of the request comprises identification of potentially relevant biobanks and other data resources in the findability services connected to the Negotiator: currently these are BBMRI-ERIC Directory, GBA Directory, GBA Locator and RD-Connect Registry and Biobank Finder. The first phase of group communication in the Negotiator is the refinement of request. Representatives of any facility can take the lead, by asking for further information from the requester. When the request is detailed enough, each facility can highlight material/data availability and accessibility for the required purpose. The requester then selects which resources to move forward with.

The platform provides a chat functionality where researchers and biobank representatives can communicate privately, allowing discussions on more sensitive topics such as access costs. The platform is compliant to the BBMRI-ERIC Access Policy⁵.

The second part is tracking of the request. The Negotiator has a complex “state machine” for each request, indicating its progress: from reviewing the request if it is compliant to the access policy of BBMRI-ERIC, biobanks indicating availability of data/samples for a particular purpose, the requester selecting her preferred biobanks, tracking of data/samples being shipped and received, to the requester announcing end of the project and dealing with the data return.

The Negotiator has already proved as an effective tool for dealing with difficult requests where many biobanks need to be contacted to check availability of material/data for a particular purpose.

⁵ <https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/services/access-policies/>

It is anticipated that other research infrastructures who use ARIA may wish to implement new functionality for group communications within the proposal submission workflows, and the experience of ARIADNE and the BBMRI Negotiator Tool will be invaluable as tools are further refined and modified.

2.4 Improving User experience at the Instruct-ERIC website

One of the reasons leading to the development of ARIADNE was the understanding that new users often find the Instruct proposal submission process quite challenging to navigate, and ARIADNE sought to assist users through the process. During ensuing discussions, it became clear that Instruct-ULTRA could focus on analysing the user experience of the Instruct-ERIC website as a whole, in order to identify areas for improvement.

2.4.1 Aims of the User Experience Study

As part of Instruct-ULTRA's work to expand access provision and new services, a new focus has been on improving user understanding of, and ability to find out about, new and existing services available through Instruct. Largely, new services provided by Instruct are advertised to users through the Instruct website and this is also the route through which users apply for access. Therefore, the website plays a key role in the successful implementation of new services. The website is also at the core of Instruct's initial relationship with users, providing key information on what Instruct is, and plays a key role in attracting scientists to apply for access to Instruct's services. In order to successfully implement new services that are accessible for users, the Instruct website needs to be clear and user-friendly. Therefore, Instruct-ULTRA has undertaken usability testing of the website, to determine how the user experience of the website can be improved. A User Experience Expert was employed at the Instruct hub to direct this significant study.

The overarching aims of the Instruct website user testing can be summarised as follows:

- Improve user understanding of Instruct
- Improve user ability to navigate around the Instruct website
- Improve the application experience
- Increase number of proposals

To achieve these aims, the user testing focussed on two key areas: the Instruct website, with a focus on the homepage, and the Instruct proposal pathway. Specific goals were then defined for the two sections to guide the usability testing.

Goals for user testing of the homepage:

- To establish first impressions and clarity of the Instruct homepage
- Determine if users can navigate to and around the Instruct website
- Establish if users can navigate the events page
- Determine if users can find information about submitting proposals (including information from the technology catalogue)

Goals for user testing of the proposal pathway:

- To establish if users understand how to submit a proposal from the proposal guidelines page
- To determine if the field headings in the proposal pathway are clear and understandable
- To determine if users can navigate through the proposal pathway
- To establish overall impressions of the proposal pathway

2.4.2 User testing of the Instruct-ERIC website

The homepage is key in explaining to new users what Instruct is, and directing users to the Instruct service catalogue, where they can find out about the different services available through Instruct. It is therefore important that the homepage is clear and easy to understand, so that users can find the information they are looking for.

To test the website, life science PhD students were recruited to act as test participants, as their profile is similar to that of Instruct's core user group. The tests were then set up using the software Lookback – a tool that records the users screen and their voice as they carry out tasks on the Instruct website. The users are asked to explain out loud what they are thinking and what they are doing. This allows information to be gathered on how users interact with the website, what they like about the site, and what they find difficult. The feedback is then analysed to determine where changes can be made.

Figure 5. Screenshot of Lookback software. The software records the screen of the user as they carry out tasks on the Instruct website.

In the usability test of the homepage, 5 participants were given the following scenario:

‘You are a post-doctoral, structural biology student. Your supervisor has suggested that you look into Instruct-ERIC.’

The participants were then given a set of 6 tasks and were asked to think out loud whilst completing them; describing what they were looking at, what they were trying to do, and what they were thinking. The tasks they were asked to complete can be found in Appendix 1.1.

Results

The results of the website user testing highlighted several key areas for improvement. Firstly, the description of Instruct found on the homepage was not entirely clear to the participants. The layout of the homepage was also not ideal, with participants finding it difficult to navigate around the website. The navigation bar headings were also found to be unclear, which led to difficulties in the participants locating the technology catalogue.

This provided some key areas for improvement – layout of the homepage, wording used on the website, and the layout of the navigation bar.

2.4.3 User testing of the Instruct Proposal Pathway

The proposal pathway is the form that users must complete in order to apply for access to Instruct’s technology. It is a vital step in the provision of services and so the pathway should be clear and easy to use, to avoid users leaving the site before completing the application process. Testing was carried out to determine the key areas for improvement in the Instruct-ERIC proposal pathway (Figure 6). In addition, a second iteration of the proposal pathway had been created for the website of iNEXT-Discovery⁶ (Figure 7), a Horizon Europe project that also uses ARIA services, of which Instruct-ERIC is a partner. Because of this, it was possible to test two slightly different designs of the proposal pathway to determine the best points from each. The feedback could then be used to create a new pathway that would be an improvement on both previous iterations.

⁶ <https://inext-discovery.eu/>

Figure 6. Screenshot of the Instruct-ERIC proposal pathway

Figure 7. Screenshots of the iNEXT-Discovery pathway

As with the homepage user testing, 5 participants were recruited to carry out the test. They were given the following scenario:

‘You are a post-doctoral, structural biology student. You would like to apply for access to solid state NMR facilities at CERM/CIRMMP in Florence, Italy.’

The users were then automatically directed to the proposal guidelines page and were asked to navigate the proposal pathway. The tasks the participants were asked to complete can be found in Appendix 1.2.

Results

Comparing the two proposal pathway designs, the iNEXT-Discovery pathway was found to be more user friendly, with a much clearer progress panel indicating which stage of the pathway the user was on. It was noted for both the Instruct and iNEXT pathways, that it would be useful to have an interactive progress panel. This would allow users to move directly between different stages of the proposal pathway, for example if they wish to edit information that they had entered previously.

A feature that users found helpful in both pathways were the help buttons that explained in more detail the information to be entered into each form field. Despite this, there were some areas where wording could be improved to make the application process clearer.

2.4.4 How the user experience test results will be implemented

The data from the usability tests has been gathered and analysed. The next stage in implementing website improvements is to design and test improvements to the website. The potential changes to the Instruct website will be designed and tested in the following sections:

- Wording used on the Instruct-ERIC website
- Navigating the Instruct-ERIC website
- Layout of the Instruct-ERIC homepage
- Design of the Instruct-ERIC proposal pathway
- Wording used in the Instruct-ERIC proposal pathway

Several tools are available to test potential improvements to the Instruct website, without having to make any changes to the live website. This includes card sorting, which allows users to group terms under either specified or unspecified headings (Figure 8). This is a useful tool for redesigning the website navigation bar. Another tool available is wireframing, where a test version of the website can be designed, allowing the layout of the website to be tested including the positioning of key action buttons.

Figure 8. Card sorting test where users sort navigation bar sub-headings into groups. OptimalSort tool from OptimalWorkshop.

The results of the User Experience Study have been passed to the Instruct-ERIC IT development team and will feed into a larger body of work to redesign the website during 2021. With improvements to the Instruct homepage and proposal pathway, it is hoped that the number of proposals submitted per year will increase by 25%.

Summary

In summary, the ARIADNE tool was developed within the Instruct-ULTRA project and showed great promise to improve collaboration and communication during proposal submission for protein production and biophysics platforms. The tool was designed, tested, and improved, although technical issues meant that ARIADNE could not be rolled out to the public as first envisaged. In order to fulfil the original aims of ARIADNE, other initiatives were launched including improvements to the ARIA internal messaging system, the use of instant messaging applications for CryoEM facility managers, the BBMRI Negotiator tool, and a full User Experience study of the Instruct-ERIC website.

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Appendices

Appendix 1

1.1 Test questions from homepage usability testing.

Task 1

You first want to find out more about Instruct-ERIC. For this task, please stay on the Instruct homepage. You can answer the questions by speaking out loud, which will be recorded and reviewed by our team. Please take as long as you need to look at the website and answer each question – there's no time limit.

- What do you think this page is about/ what do you think you can do here/ what strikes you about this page?
- Tell us your first impressions of the homepage.
- What are your thoughts on the design and layout of the page?
- In your own words, what do you think Instruct-ERIC is?
- What services do you think Instruct-ERIC offers?
- What audience(s) do you think this page is designed for?
- Why do you think someone would want to visit the Instruct website?

Task 2

Now look specifically at the navigation bar.

- How user friendly do you think the navigation bar is?
- What are your thoughts on the choice of words used?
- Where would you expect find information about the different locations that you could visit to carry out an experiment?

Task 3

You can now move around the website freely. For the following questions, please talk through your thought process aloud.

- Find out the duration of an Instruct Internship.
- Find the dates for the FEBS 2020 Conference.
- Find the contact person for the Instruct-ERIC workshop on Image Processing for Electron Microscopy being held in June 2020.

Task 4

Scenario: You are a post-doctoral, structural biology student from the UK. Your supervisor has suggested that you look into a funded research visit at one of Instruct's Centres.

First, find out if you are eligible for a funded research visit through Instruct-ERIC.

- What funding could you receive through Instruct-ERIC?

Task 5

Scenario continued: As part of your research, you want to study the structure of a protein using the technique of cryo-electron microscopy (cryoEM). You decide to submit a proposal to Instruct-ERIC for a funded research visit to a cryoEM facility. Remember to tell us your thoughts as you go.

- Without using the search bar, what can you find out about the technologies available from Instruct-ERIC?
- More specifically, what can you find out about the cryoEM services available through Instruct-ERIC?
- Which Instruct research sites in the UK offer CryoEM?

- Find out how to apply for a research visit to one of the Instruct centres. Start the process to apply and describe the steps you are taking. *Note please don't go as far as entering any personal information.*

Task 6

- How would you describe your overall experience with the Instruct-ERIC website?
- What did you like the most about the website?
- What did you like the least?
- What, if anything, caused you frustration?
- What other information or resources would you like/expect to find on the Instruct website?

1.2 Test questions from proposal pathway usability testing.

Task 1

Without navigating away from this page:

- Tell us your first impressions of this page. What do you think this page is about?
- Find the stages of the application process. What do you understand by these stages?
- Assuming that you had not used Instruct services before, what is the first step you would need to take to start an application?
- Find where to click to start the application process.

Task 2

You want to apply for access to solution solid state NMR (nuclear magnetic resonance) facilities at CERM/CIRMMP.

- Without entering any information/clicking anything on the page:
- What do you think you can do on this page?
- What strikes you about this page?
- How many steps are there in the proposal submission process?

Task 3

You want to apply for one visit to the solid state NMR technology in Italy.

- What are your thoughts on the layout/list structure for selecting technology?
- How easy is it to find the locations that offer solid state NMR?

Move on to the second stage of the proposal submission process and confirm your selection.

Task 4

Have a look at the proposal details page without entering any information.

- What do you understand by each of the headings?
- Are there any headings that you think don't make sense, or could be clearer?
- Now enter the research project title as 'Test'.

Task 5

You, Callum Smith, are the principle investigator for the research visit, and your homelab colleague is Giselle Adams. Your supervisor is Prof A Davies and he previously worked at the Instruct-UK centre.

- Enter the information which you think would be appropriate for 'Your research team' and 'Exclude reviewers'.

Task 6

You realise that you forgot to enter NAME as a home lab colleague in your proposal.

- Correct this information in your proposal.
- When you have corrected this information, please complete and submit the proposal.

Task 7

- How would you describe your overall experience with the Instruct-ERIC proposal pathway?
- What did you like the most about the system?
- What did you like the least?
- What, if anything, caused you frustration?